

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D3.4 - SHARING SYSTEM REPORT

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document is the ePLANET's deliverable 3.4, which explains how the platform is connected to external sources and visualisations.

It is developed a bidirectional communication to the external sources. For one side is gathered data to fulfil the platform data needs. For the other side is developed the exportation capacities in order to communicate the data gathered and harmonised outside the developed platform.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
DSO	Distributor System Operator
GCoM	Global Covenant of Mayors
JRC	Joint Research Center
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
PV	Photovoltaics
UC	Use Case

1 Introduction

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action co-funded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims at deploying new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This goal is reached by integrating many data sources into one unique platform to simplify the energy transition agents' work and provide a complete municipality overview. Moreover, as the ePLANET platform has unified all this data in a common framework, it aims to be a data provider tool to these technicians. On one side, it provides data to some regional visualisation platforms, and on the other, it provides easy ways to export all the already treated data from the platform.

This document explains all the data sources used and the platform exportation capabilities, providing a complete understanding of this data integration work.

2 Data imports

The main objective of this section is to provide a clear and comprehensive view of the fundamental data sources that support the various functionalities and services offered on the ePLANET platform. Every application and database plays an essential role in providing accurate and up-to-date information. Furthermore, this information is key for future updates and improvements.

For this reason, below is a full breakdown of each database used, including a brief description, their purpose and the specific contributions they make to the ePLANET platform.

2.1 Applications and data sources feeding ePLANET

1.	JRC - GCOM - MyCovenant	UC: 1 Pilot: Crete Island
<p>Data description: The Joint Research Center (JRC) serves as the European Commission's science and knowledge arm, conducting research endeavors aimed at providing independent scientific counsel and policy support to the European Union.</p> <p>The dataset utilised within the project pertains to a comprehensive collection of action plans and monitoring reports from the MyCovenant reporting platform, situated within the framework of the Global Covenant of Mayors (GCoM) initiative. This dataset is released biannually and encompasses the data reported to the CoM (Covenant of Mayors). It is important to note that this dataset offers a partial perspective due to the incomplete reporting of actions to the CoM.</p> <p>Link: https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/id-00354</p> <p>Sharing format: .xls file</p> <p>Data acquisition: The acquisition of this dataset was a straightforward process, primarily involving manual downloads from the JRC platform (the files accessible through the provided hyperlink). These files, in xls format, were obtained and subsequently uploaded to the ePLANET project database. An essential step in this process was the implementation of a harmonisation procedure to standardise data formats to have a consistent dataset.</p> <p>Data Use: The Crete pilot does not have access to the SECAP templates or working material from the SECAP developments. The pilot could provide PDFs of the energy transition plans with no organised structure to automatically pick up the information. For this, to gather the SECAPs data, the data provided by the JRC is used. In this dataset, there is missing data like the investments or data description of the measure, but the gross amount of SECAP data is obtained from this source.</p>		

2.	SECAP Data	UC: 1 Pilot: Crete Island
<p>Data description: The SECAP document presented by the municipalities to report the energy transition plan to the CoM portal.</p>		

Link/More info: https://eu-mayors.ec.europa.eu/en/action_plan_list

Sharing format: PDF

Data acquisition: This data is manually collected by the partners.

Data Use: This data is gathered from the SECAPs documents because there is no other available data source to pick this data from. This data is used to complete the description of the actions reported by the JRC.

3.	SECAPs Template	UC: 1 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: The Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) template constitutes the standard reporting framework for Covenant Signatories. The SECAP template forms the skeleton of the individual action plans. The SECAP and its monitoring part allow signatories to collect and analyse data in a structured and systematic manner, serve as a basis for good climate and energy management and for tracking progress in implementation.</p> <p>Link/More info: https://eu-mayors.ec.europa.eu/en/resources/reporting</p> <p>Sharing format: Excel</p> <p>Data acquisition: The municipalities/regions or the consulting agency contracted by them to develop the SECAP used this template to report the SECAPs to the CoM. They have provided us with these Excel files from which we have gathered the energy consumption, emissions and the key actions.</p> <p>Data Use: These files have been mapped and harmonised to the ePLANET data model (consumption, emissions and key actions). The key actions have been only used temporally in the platform meanwhile, all the actions were harmonised. When the actions have been harmonised the key actions have been removed from the platform because they were in English and have been replaced by all the actions considered in the transition plans, which all are in the regional language.</p>		

4.	SECAP working files for Girona	UC: 1 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: The Girona Province pilot provides the working files to develop the energy transition plans. On one side, they provide the SECAP Templates already explained in the data source 3. However, the recent version of the SECAP template only reported the key actions, not all the actions. To track and manage the energy transition plan execution, a complete list of actions is needed. These ones are reported on the SECAP document (in PDF) with difficult gathering possibilities. For this, the working editable documents from the consultancies contracted by the municipalities are used to develop the energy transition plans. All the energy transition plans have been developed by 5 different consultancies (ARDA, ARUM, ECOSERVEIS and OICOS) with their own way of working, so with their own data formats.</p>		

Link/More info: -

Sharing format: Excel

Data acquisition: All the actions information from the provided files has been gathered and harmonised to the ePLANET data model. This harmonisation process has been complex because all the consultancies have their own taxonomy in the action's definition. This means that each consultancy has been defined as a taxonomy conversion from the consultancy taxonomy to the standard taxonomy used in the ePLANET ontology.

Data Use: This data is displayed in the ePLANET platform visualisation module to the energy transition technicians, providing a dynamic environment to filter and track the development of energy transition plans. It also provides a transversal view to all the energy transition actions from all the municipalities in the same place, making the identification of similar initiatives from different energy transition plans easy. This could help grow synergies between municipalities and give examples of how municipalities face the same challenges differently.

5.	Consumption/Emissions reported in Girona (IRE/ISE)	UC: 1 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: As part of monitoring the SECAPs, it is necessary to see the evolution of the emissions of the signatory municipalities. This is why DDGI has collected the emission monitoring inventories (ISE) for each of the municipalities. The reference year for which the emission reduction results will be compared is 2005.</p> <p>The IRE (emission reference inventory), is a prerequisite for preparing the SECAPs, this data source is fed with some data from the IRE but also includes the emissions and consumption data from the municipal buildings, municipal vehicles and public transport. Unlike the ISE, which provides data from all the municipalities, each municipality has one specific IRE.</p> <p>Link/More info: -</p> <p>Sharing format: Excel</p> <p>Data acquisition: Both typologies of Excel were harmonised. The municipal global consumption and emissions by sector and energy vector are gathered from the ISE and the municipality consumption and emissions from public buildings, public lighting, municipal vehicles and public transport are gathered from the IRE.</p> <p>Data Use: This data is visualised in the visualisation module of UC1, providing a municipal overview of the energy consumption and emissions.</p>		

6.	DATADIS (Spanish electric DSO platform)	UC: 1 & 3 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: DATADIS is the Spanish DSOs common platform where users can access their electrical energy consumption. This platform provides two types of data: the postal code level aggregated energy consumption discretised by sector on an hourly basis, which is public and the consumer hourly energy consumption, which can be accessed by the consumer and third parties authorised by the consumer.</p> <p>Link/More info: https://datadis.es</p> <p>Sharing format: CSV/JSON</p> <p>Data acquisition: The communication with DATADIS is carried out through their API. The API has two parts: the public one, which provides aggregated data at postal code, and the private data, which requires the specific credentials to access the authorised client consumption. To get access to the specific municipal buildings, all the municipalities provide their authorisation to access this data. Moreover, to simplify the data management to get all the authorisations to the same user, the authorisation of one representative from the Catalan government was required. Once all these authorisations were presented and validated by the DSOs platform, they provided the credentials to access all the required municipal data. Then, the data could be harmonised and stored in the project common database.</p> <p>Data Use: The postal code aggregated data by sectors has been used in the UC3. In this UC is used the monthly building electrical consumption from all the buildings (public and private) from a municipality (gathered from the data source 9). To plan possible energy communities based on PV is crossed the hourly postal code energy consumption with the monthly building energy consumption.</p> <p>The data provided by the private part of DATADIS is used to gather the electrical consumption from the municipal buildings and public lighting to be able to collect this data automatically. Therefore, at least for electrical consumption, this data could be updated automatically in the SECAPs tracking.</p>		

7.	Electricity consumption in public buildings in Crete (billing information)	UC: 2 Pilot: Crete Island
<p>Data description: The Crete pilot municipal buildings' energy consumption is reported by some Excels files provided by the DSOs. Each municipality provides at least one Excel file with the electricity billing information. RDFC has modified these Excels to identify the headers of the Excels, unifying the reporting format.</p> <p>Link/More info: -</p> <p>Sharing format: Excel</p> <p>Data acquisition: The Excels modified by RDFC were mapped in order to gather all the data. A cleaning stage had to be implemented in order to identify estimated billing and rely only on real measurements. Through the real measurements and considering the</p>		

measurement dates, the daily energy consumption could be estimated and aggregated at a monthly level.

Data Use: This data is presented in the visualisation module of UC2. The target is to proportionate the data in a visual way for the technicians to analyse the energy consumption trend in the buildings. Moreover, the platform is prepared to export the data in simple formats to provide the required information for the technicians if they need further analysis.

8.	Communication Microsoft Acces via pre-established format (Zlin Region)	UC: 2 Pilot: Zlín Region
<p>Data description: EAZK has its own public buildings' energy consumption database in a Microsoft Acces format. This database contains the monthly electricity, gas, district heating, coal and water consumption by each building.</p> <p>Link/More info: -</p> <p>Sharing format: Excel</p> <p>Data acquisition: As their database version and the ePLANET database technologies are incompatible, an Excel format was agreed to import this data to the platform. There have been agreed two types of Excel. The first one has all the static data from all the 377 buildings included in the platform. This data identifies the building, direction, geolocalisation, owner and energy efficiency measures (EEM) applied to them. The second Excel type agreed is the actual consumption of these buildings. For this second format, EAZK generated one Excel file for each building. These Excel formats were mapped and the data has been harmonised to the ePLANET data model.</p> <p>Data Use: This data is presented in the visualisation module of UC2. The target is to proportionate the data visually for the technicians to analyse the energy consumption trend in the buildings. Moreover, as the pilot provided EEMs, this data is used to assess the impact of the EEMs.</p>		

9.	Electricity DSO data export directly provided by DSO	UC: 3 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: Monthly electrical energy consumption at the building level for all the buildings of the pilot municipalities with more than 4 different consumption points. This restriction of buildings with more than 4 consumption points is required for the DSO to follow the consumer's data protection laws.</p> <p>Link/More info: -</p> <p>Sharing format: CSV/Excel</p> <p>Data acquisition: This data is provided directly from the DSO. In order to get it, the municipalities have sent a letter to the DSO requiring for this data. As a public administration, the DSO should provide this data to them. Once this data was obtained, it</p>		

was harmonised into the ePLANET data model and incorporated into the ePLANET database.

Data Use: This data is used in the UC3 to develop a tool to help users design their energy communities. As the Spanish regulation has a minimum distance requirement for all the energy community, it was required to know the possible members' consumption georeferenced.

10.	Gas consumption provided directly from DSO	UC: 3 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: Annual gas consumption at building level for all the buildings in the pilot municipalities with more than 4 consumption points. This restriction of buildings with more than 4 consumption points is required for the DSO to follow the consumer's data protection laws.</p> <p>Link/More info: -</p> <p>Sharing format: CSV</p> <p>Data acquisitions: This data is provided directly from the gas DSO. In order to get it, the municipalities have sent a letter to the DSO requiring for this data. As a public administration the DSO should provide this data to them. Once this data was obtained it was harmonized into the ePLANET data model and incorporated to the ePLANET database.</p> <p>Data Use: This data is used in the UC3 to develop a tool to help users in designing their energy communities based on PV generation. The gas consumption is needed in order to consider the users global energy consumption to also promote the user's change from using fossil fuels to electricity. As the Spanish regulation has a minimum distance requirement for all the energy community it was required to know the possible members consumption georeferenced.</p>		

11.	INSPIRES Cadastral format	UC: 3 Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Data description: The INSPIRE Directive aims to create a European Union spatial data infrastructure for the purposes of EU environmental policies and policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment. One of the themes of this infrastructure is the Cadastral Parcels data. As many European countries are adopting this standard, enabling the connection and defining the harmonisation procedure to the ePLANET database facilitates the cadastral data collection.</p> <p>Link/More info: https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/</p> <p>Sharing format: GML</p> <p>Data acquisition: This is public data which have been harmonised and stored in the ePLANET database.</p> <p>Data Use: This data has been used to georeference the electricity and gas consumption from UC3. The provided consumption data has been provided with the building address. It</p>		

has been used a fuzzy logic algorithm to link this text field with the building cadastral information. Between all the fields defined in the cadastre there is the latitude and longitude which enables to locate where the consumption is made. This step is required in order to follow the Spanish regulation which indicates that all the energy community must be in one area range.

12.	LAUS	UC: All Use Cases Pilot: All Pilots
<p>Data description: LAUs (Local Administrative Units) are the building blocks of the NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) and statistical regions, and comprise the municipalities and communes of the European Statistical System (ESS). Data is available annually and includes total resident population figures per LAU.</p> <p>Link/More info: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/lau#lau19</p> <p>Sharing format: GeoJSON</p> <p>Data acquisition: This data is publicly available and has been imported to the harmonization module, as a taxonomy and a way of identifying and locating the georeferenced data.</p> <p>Data Use: This data is incorporated in the ePLANET harmonisation modules in order to identify in which local administrative division is each consumption.</p>		

13.	NUTS	UC: All Use Cases Pilot: All Pilots
<p>Data description: The GISCO statistical unit dataset represents the NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) and Statistical regions through multipart polygon, polyline and point topology. The NUTS geographical information is completed by attribute tables and a set of cartographic helplines to visualise multipart polygonal regions better.</p> <p>The NUTS are a hierarchical system divided into 3 levels. NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions, NUTS 2: basic regions for the application of regional policies, NUTS 3: small regions for specific diagnoses. Additionally, a NUTS 0 level, usually co-incident with national boundaries are also available.</p> <p>Link/More info: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/administrative-units-statistical-units/nuts#nuts21</p> <p>Sharing format: GeoJSON</p> <p>Data acquisition: This data is publicly available and has been imported to the harmonisation module as a taxonomy and a way of identifying and locating the georeferenced data.</p> <p>Data Use: This data is incorporated in the ePLANET harmonisation modules to identify in which NUTS division is each consumption.</p>		

14.	EUBUCCO	UC: 4 Pilot: Zlín Region
<p>Data description: EUBUCCO is a scientific database of individual building footprints for 200+ million buildings across the 27 European Union countries and Switzerland.</p> <p>Link/More info: https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-023-02040-2</p> <p>Sharing format: GPKG</p> <p>Data acquisitions: The data file which is publicly available has been filtered to have only data from the Zlín region and has been harmonised and stored in the ePLANET database.</p> <p>Data Use: The shape of the buildings was needed to develop the UC4 (roof PV potential estimation) to simplify the building recognition from the LIDAR scan. For this, this database of building footprint was used as a cutting tool to subset the building scan from all its surroundings and proceed with the roof identification.</p>		

15.	Zlín Region LiDAR data	UC: 4 Pilot: Zlín Region
<p>Data description: The Zlín region LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) data is obtained through an aerial region scan. This scan provides a cloud of points, which indicates the georeferenced height of the scanned points. This cloud of points defines the shape and the height of the buildings scanned, enabling roof detection.</p> <p>Link/More info: -</p> <p>Sharing format: TXT files with the coordinates and height of the scanned points.</p> <p>Data acquisition: The data has been provided by EAZK and manipulated in QGIS.</p> <p>Data Use: This data is manipulated and prepared to be used in QGIS. Using this data together with the building footprint, the point cloud of the building is obtained. This cloud of points is analysed to detect all the roofs' planes and tilts to determine the PV potential of each building.</p>		

3 Data exports

To accomplish the project goal of facilitating the municipal energy transition, the municipalities need to have all the data available to spread the stage in which they are and report it.

For this, the platform is communicated with two visualisation platforms and enables easy export of all the data and graphics from the visual interface.

3.1 Applications and databases fed by ePLANET

1.	SITMUN	Pilot: Girona Province
<p>Platform description: SITMUN (Municipal Territorial Information System) is a visualisation platform of different types of municipal data based on a territorial map of the Girona Province.</p> <p>What data is exported: Municipal energy consumption and emissions by sectors. The data provided to the visualisation platform is the data provided by the SECAP plans, which have been digitalised.</p> <p>Sharing format: JSON</p>		

2.	Geospatial Information Portal of the Region of Crete	Pilot: Crete Island
<p>Platform description: The Geospatial Information Portal of the Region of Crete is a visualisation portal based on a GIS environment where a large variety of data is displayed. In this platform, the data can be georeferenced into one point or displayed at the municipal level.</p> <p>What data is exported: The municipal buildings' energy consumption aggregated by municipalities.</p> <p>Sharing format: SHP (shape files).</p>		

3.2 Generic exportation method

The visualisation platform is prepared to export all the data displayed. Figure 3-1 presents the aggregated energy consumption of one municipality. As shown in the figure, there is the possibility to export all the data in Excel format and the graphics in PNG, JPG, PDF, and SVG.

Figure 3-1 Municipal data visualisation

Figure 3-2 presents the monthly energy consumption table of one building. As indicated in the top right button, this data can be exported in Excel.

Monthly detail. Export data to Excel						
Month	2020			2021		
	Electricity	Gas and fuels	Total	Electricity	Gas and fuels	Total
January	30.980	1.228.649	1.259.629	31.659	1.214.760	1.246.419
February	29.854	915.081	944.935	30.698	1.028.703	1.059.401
March	29.584	807.326	836.910	30.461	680.893	711.354
April	28.987	636.115	665.102	28.974	541.290	570.264
May	28.546	456.283	484.829	27.987	485.138	513.125
June	27.235	246.759	273.994	26.854	317.758	344.612
July	26.548	120.087	146.635	26.526	94.465	120.991
August	27.584	131.701	159.285	26.352	118.172	144.524
September	28.654	397.976	426.630	27.854	426.711	454.565
October	29.654	547.636	577.290	29.649	703.282	732.931
November	29.548	807.685	837.233	30.564	812.235	842.799
December	30.658	1.145.438	1.176.096	31.521	1.107.484	1.139.005
Totals	347.832	7.440.736	7.788.568	349.099	7.530.891	7.879.990

Figure 3-2 Building energy consumption

Figure 3-3 shows Chania municipality actions from the SECAP. As indicated in the top right of the table, this data can also be exported.

Planning

Project: Everyone | Tipologia de plan: E-PLANET SUSTAINABLE ENERGY AND CLIMATE ACTION PLANS (SECAP) | Sector: 7 Selected | Date: 2022 - 2022

Delete filters | Export

Project	Plan	Measure	Sector	Intervention area	Category of Use	Start date	End date	Responsible	Cost (€)	Energy savings (kWh)	Renewable production (kWh)	Execution status (%)
E-Planet - Crete - Chanion	CHANIA ACTI...	Supply ...	Transport	Others	Fleet	01/01/2019	31/12/2022	Municipality/... SA	0	0	0	0
E-Planet - Crete - Chanion	CHANIA ACTI...	Renewal...	Transport	Others	Mobility	01/01/2019	31/12/2023	Municipality	0	0	0	0
E-Planet - Crete - Chanion	CHANIA ACTI...	Replace ...	Others	Others	Services	01/01/2018	31/12/2023	Municipality	0	0	0	0

Figure 3-3 Energy transition measures

These export capabilities allow the platform's available data to be easily exported and introduced to any other platform.

4 Conclusions

A complete set of harmonisation and integration procedures is developed to fulfil the platform's data needs. This process ensures that all the data collected from all the different sources are harmonised into the same database and taxonomy, ensuring that they are all comparable between them. To accomplish this result, there has been a study of all the data sources and, in many cases, collaboration with the data suppliers. The data have been integrated from many different sources however, many have been provided by the pilot regions. To gather this data, which in many cases wasn't in any standard format, it has been agreed with a communication format in Excel files.

To take advantage of the data integration done, the platform is ready to communicate the required data to the visualisation tools of Girona province and Crete island. Moreover, to make the platform more valuable to the municipalities and to help them use other tools if needed, the platform is prepared to easily export the harmonised data in simple formats to be used with external tools.

